

I.FAST

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MILESTONE REPORT

Hypothesis on the causes of the instabilities of the focal spot profile

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ABSTRACT

This document describes the hypothesis for beam pointing instabilities on the basis of measurements done on the Apollon Laser Facility. Based on this observation, an action plan will be carried out to find ways to improve the stability of the profile of the focal task.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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1 Introduction

WP 6 of the I-FAST project is dealing with compact plasma accelerators.

These accelerators are approaching their implementation phase following the dramatic development of laser wakefield acceleration.

Performances are expected to be limited by several factors, one of the most challenging being the high intensity laser driver stability on target, whose specifications are dictated by the choice of laser plasma acceleration.

One of the factors of intensity instabilities is focal spot size and shape instabilities, since pulse duration and pulse energy are already quite stable.

This document confirms through measurements the hypothesis of the causes of the focal spot shape instabilities.

2 Hypothesis

The distortion of the focal spot is due to changes in the wave front of the laser beam before focusing.

Wave front changes are closely linked to changes in the media through which the laser beam passes.

The lasers used for particle acceleration are femtosecond lasers. These femtosecond lasers are mostly based on the CPA technique and therefore rely on a stretcher and a compressor. From then on, the beam from the entry of the compressor is under vacuum up to the target. Being under vacuum, the instabilities of the medium are, if not zero, very minimal.

It is therefore assumed that the instabilities impacting the wave front are located in the front-end stages (generation of the beam) and the amplification stages and up to the compressor entry.

When one thinks of these stages, there are two types of mediums which are crossed by the laser: the air between each optical component the optical components which are the lenses and the amplifying mediums (crystals, slabs, ...).

Concerning the optical components, the deformations of the wave front that they can bring will be stable and therefore will not lead to instability.

The only optical components which could cause instabilities are the amplifiers whose state changes during the passage of the beam. However, it is assumed that once a steady state of laser operation has been reached (thermal conditions established) the instabilities introduced exist but are weak.

We conclude that the main disturbances come from instabilities in the air through which the beam passes.

3 Instabilities due to air turbulences

The hypothesis is then that air turbulences are the main cause for these instabilities, but the extent and characteristics were unknown. So we have decided to make a campaign of measurement on the Apollon laser facility.

3.1 SET-UP

The main goal of this campaign was to measure the impact of turbulence in the amplification stages.

In order to measure the temporal evolution of the wave front, we needed to employ a Continuous Wave (CW) light source and a sufficiently fast wave front sensor.

Figure 1 : Top view of the amplification area.

We used two different sources, depending on the measurement. The first one was a very large spectrum oscillator, which was injected early in the system and therefore collected all dynamic aberrations on the amplification table. The second one was a monochromatic CW Diode.

In Fig. 1, the location of the fiber termination is marked as ①, while the expanded beam was injected right before the last afocal telescope. The location is marked with ②. Like this, the diode excluded the largest part of the beam path on the optical table and enabled us to separate its dynamic aberrations from the ones accumulated afterwards.

We were able to reduce the beam path in air by inserting a mirror in position ③ in Fig. 1.

The deformable mirror was located in position ④ in Fig. 1.

The wave front sensor was located in mark ⑤ in Fig. 1.

3.2 DATA EVALUATION

The criteria used to evaluate these variations is the Strehl ratio. Figure 2 shows the evolution of the spatial phase and of the Strehl ratio on a time of 20 seconds. We see that the Strehl ratio varies from 0.25 to 0.85.

Figure 2 : Measurements made in the amplification zone.

Figure 3: wave front RMS and Strehl ratio of the beam without and with by pass, where the diode source is used

Obviously, both configurations suffer from dynamic aberrations. However, the quality of the beam without the by-pass is much worse, featuring occasional intensity drops of a factor of four within a single second.

The spectral analysis of the measurements, based on the Evaluation Gradient Jitter Spectra, shows that beyond 70 Hz the disturbances are minimal and that the majority of the disturbances are at low frequencies (up to 0.1 Hz). These measurements were reproduced by stopping the airflow of the amplification room. Apparently, venting does impact the dynamic aberrations between 0.5 Hz and 50 Hz. However, the effect only becomes apparent when the beam does not use the by-pass, indicating that the magnitude of the aberrations in the longer path is an order of magnitude larger and mask out the change of venting.

These showed a clear improvement indicating that the instabilities beyond 0.1 Hz were essentially related to atmospheric disturbances through which the beam is transported.

Figure 4 : Spectral analysis of beam disturbances.

In order to determine if a significant contribution to the turbulence occurs in the first amplification stages, we compared the wave front spectrum using the diode beam and the large spectrum oscillator, which is injected earlier in the system. Any difference would correspond to dynamic aberrations accumulated in the first amplification stages. Fig. 5 shows the corresponding spectra.

We can notice that:

- the high end of the spectrum shows the pattern of different signal-to-noise ratios. This is due to the large band oscillator being more powerful and better illuminated at the edges.
- the difference in the main part of the spectrum is only small and close to the threshold of statistical significance. Roughly speaking, the difference cannot contribute more than 50% of the energy spectrum below 30 Hz and is likely much lower.

Figure 5: Spectra of the beam without bypass using diode and the large band oscillator

The graph of figure 5, where we removed covers of the first amplifier stages where it shows no changes in the spectrum. This makes us think that the differences in figure 5 may be measurement errors from using different light sources.

Figure 6: Spectra using the large spectrum oscillator beam under changes of the cover situation of the amp table

It is to know that on these stages the diameter of the beam is approximately 5mm, then 55mm, whereas it is 140 mm in the last amplifier. The fact that the beam is larger implies that the variations are spatially larger except to say that the fluctuations of the air are spatially identical which is totally false.

3.3 SOURCES OF AIR FLUCTUATIONS

We made several tests to find what causes air fluctuations in the amplification section.

The more important sources were heat sources like CCD, power supplies, gauges and motors.

But we were also able to determine that some devices link pumping system could generate small fluctuations probably due to acoustic waves.

4 Conclusion

Our hypothesis saying that the first source of instabilities of the shape of the focal spot were the disturbances on long distance and the fluctuations related to the air is verified.

It seems that if we keep the beam size under a given diameter the impact of air fluctuations is really small and comparable to other sources of fluctuations. We could do a study and try to determine what is the maximum diameter that we could accept.

Another idea could be then to put all the amplification under vacuum to avoid air fluctuations, but this solution is not really economically viable.

Our idea is now set up a fast correction loop ($> 200\text{Hz}$ related to our 70Hz fluctuations) in order to correct the observed instabilities in the wave front thus in the focal spot.

Once this fast loop has been set up and qualified, we will be able to remeasure the variations in the shape of the focal spot. We may then be able to detect other sources of instability that we have in this first phase considered negligible in the amplifying media.

Before going further in this study, it will of course be necessary to check whether the stability obtained is not already sufficient for the use of lasers in the acceleration of particles and the generation of stable electron beams.